

ON AN EXPRESSION FOR ${}_2F_1\left(n + \frac{1}{2}, n + 1; n + \frac{3}{2}; -1\right)$

R. Sivaraman*, M. MuniruIddrisu & J. López-Bonilla*****

* Department of Mathematics, Dwaraka Doss Goverdhan Doss Vaishnav College, Chennai, India

** Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Physical Sciences, University for Development Studies, Tamale, Ghana

*** ESIME-Zacatenco, National Polytechnic Institute, Building 4, 1st Apartment, Col. Lindavista CP 07738, CDMX, Mexico

Cite This Article: R. Sivaraman, M. MuniruIddrisu & J. López-Bonilla, "On an Expression for ${}_2F_1\left(n + \frac{1}{2}, n + 1; n + \frac{3}{2}; -1\right)$ ", International Journal of Applied and Advanced Scientific Research, Volume 9, Issue 2, July - December, Page Number 113-114, 2024.

Copy Right: © DV Publication, 2024 (All Rights Reserved). This is an Open Access Article distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium provided the original work is properly cited.

Abstract:

Recently Feng Qi obtained an expression for ${}_2F_1\left(n + \frac{1}{2}, n + 1; n + \frac{3}{2}; -1\right)$, here we deduce an alternative formula for this Gauss hypergeometric function.

Key Words: Gauss Hyper Geometric Function, Gamma Function.

1. Introduction:

Feng Qi [1] obtained the relation:

$${}_2F_1\left(n + \frac{1}{2}, n + 1; n + \frac{3}{2}; -1\right) = \frac{(2n+1)!!}{(2n)!!} \frac{\pi}{4} + \frac{2n+1}{2^{2n}} \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{(-1)^k}{k} \binom{2n-k}{n} 2^{k/2} \sin \frac{3k\pi}{4}, \quad n \geq 0, \quad (1)$$

for the Gauss hyper geometric function [2-6]. In Sec. 2 we deduce an alternative expression for (1) in terms of the gamma function [7-9].

2. On the Qi's Formula:

We know the property [5]:

$$\begin{aligned} {}_2F_1(a, b; c; z) &= \frac{\Gamma(c) \Gamma(b-a)}{\Gamma(c-a) \Gamma(b)} (-z)^{-a} {}_2F_1\left(a, 1-c+a; 1-b+a; \frac{1}{z}\right) \\ &+ {}_2F_1\left(\frac{c}{c-b}, \frac{c}{c-b}; \frac{c}{c-b}; -z\right) (-z)^{-b} {}_2F_1\left(b, 1-c+b; 1-a+b; \frac{1}{z}\right), \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Which for $a = n + \frac{1}{2}$, $b = n + 1$, $c = n + \frac{3}{2}$, $z = -1$ implies the identity:

$${}_2F_1\left(n + \frac{1}{2}, n + 1; n + \frac{3}{2}; -1\right) = \frac{\pi (2n+1)!}{2^{2n+1} (n!)^2} - (2n+1) {}_2F_1\left(n + 1, \frac{1}{2}; \frac{3}{2}; -1\right), \quad (3)$$

Where were used the following values of the gamma function [7-9]:

$$\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) = \sqrt{\pi}, \quad \Gamma\left(-\frac{1}{2}\right) = -2\sqrt{\pi}, \quad \Gamma(n+1) = n!, \quad \Gamma\left(n + \frac{1}{2}\right) = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}(2n)!}{2^{2n} n!}, \quad \Gamma\left(n + \frac{3}{2}\right) = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}(2n+1)!}{2^{2n+1} n!}. \quad (4)$$

On the other hand, Li-Qi [10] deduced the relation:

$${}_2F_1(a, b; a-b-j+1; -1) = \frac{\sqrt{\pi} \Gamma(a-b-j+1)}{2^a \Gamma\left(\frac{a-2b-j+1}{2}\right) \Gamma\left(\frac{a-2b-j+2}{2}\right)} \sum_{r=0}^j \binom{j}{r} \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{a-2b-j+r+1}{2}\right)}{\Gamma\left(\frac{a-j+r+1}{2}\right)}, \quad (5)$$

Where we can employ the values $a = n + 1$, $b = \frac{1}{2}$, $j = n$ to obtain the expression:

$${}_2F_1\left(n + 1, \frac{1}{2}; \frac{3}{2}; -1\right) = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2^{n+2}} \sum_{r=0}^n \binom{n}{r} \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{r+1}{2}\right)}{\Gamma\left(\frac{r+2}{2}\right)} = \frac{1}{2^{n+2}} \sum_{r=0}^n \binom{n}{r} \frac{2^r}{r!} \left[\Gamma\left(\frac{r+1}{2}\right)\right]^2, \quad (6)$$

Thus, for example:

$${}_2F_1\left(1, \frac{1}{2}; \frac{3}{2}; -1\right) = \frac{\pi}{4}, \quad (7)$$

$${}_2F_1\left(2, \frac{1}{2}; \frac{3}{2}; -1\right) = \frac{\pi}{8} + \frac{1}{4}. \quad (8)$$

Hence from (3) and (6):

$${}_2F_1\left(n + \frac{1}{2}, n + 1; n + \frac{3}{2}; -1\right) = \frac{\pi (2n+1)!}{2^{2n+1} (n!)^2} - \frac{2n+1}{2^{n+2}} \sum_{r=0}^n \binom{n}{r} \frac{2^r}{r!} \left[\Gamma\left(\frac{r+1}{2}\right)\right]^2, \quad (9)$$

As an alternative to (1) deduced by Feng Qi [1].

Remark 1:

We know the formula [1, 4, 5, 10]:

$${}_2F_1\left(1, \frac{1}{2}; \frac{3}{2}; -z^2\right) = \frac{1}{z} \arctan z, \quad (10)$$

Which for $z = 1$ implies (7).

Remark 2:

Li-Qi [10] obtained the following identities:

$${}_2F_1(a, b; a-b+1; -1) = \frac{\sqrt{\pi} \Gamma(a-b+1)}{2^a \Gamma\left(\frac{a-b+1}{2}\right) \Gamma\left(\frac{a+1}{2}\right)}, \quad (11)$$

$${}_2F_1(a+1, b; a-b+1; -1) = \frac{\sqrt{\pi} \Gamma(a-b+1)}{2^{a+1}} \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma\left(\frac{a+1}{2}\right) \Gamma\left(\frac{a}{2}-b+1\right)} + \frac{1}{\Gamma\left(\frac{a}{2}+1\right) \Gamma\left(\frac{a+1}{2}-b\right)} \right], \quad (12)$$

Which for $a = 1, b = \frac{1}{2}$ imply (7) and (8), respectively.

Remark 3:

The comparison of (1) and (9) gives the interesting relation:

$$\sum_{k=1}^n \frac{(-1)^k}{k} \binom{2n-k}{n} 2^{k/2} \operatorname{Sin} \frac{3k\pi}{4} = \frac{\pi (2n)!}{4 (n!)^2} - \sqrt{\pi} 2^{n-2} \sum_{r=0}^n \binom{n}{r} \frac{2^r}{r!} \left[\Gamma \left(\frac{r+1}{2} \right) \right]^2 \quad (13)$$

References:

1. Feng Qi, Power series expansion of Wilf function, arXiv: 2110.08576v3 [math.CO] 29 Jul 2024.
2. J. Dutka, The early history of the hypergeometric function, Arch. Hist. Exact Sci. 31, No. 1 (1984), 15-34.
3. J. B. Seaborn, Hypergeometric functions and their applications, Springer, New York, USA (1991).
4. N. M. Temme, Special functions: An introduction to the classical functions of mathematical physics, Wiley, New York (1996).
5. J. Pearson, Computation of hypergeometric functions, Master of Science Thesis, University of Oxford, England (2009).
6. F. W. J. Olver, D. W. Lozier, R. F. Boisvert, Ch. W. Clark, NIST handbook of mathematical functions, Cambridge University Press (2010).
7. G. K. Srinivasan, The gamma function: An eclectic tour, Am. Math. Monthly 114, No. 4 (2007) 297-315.
8. H. M. Srivastava, J. Choi, Zeta and q-zeta functions and associated series and integrals, Elsevier, London (2012).
9. J. Patricia Hannah, Identities for the gamma and hypergeometric functions: an overview from Euler to the present, Master of Science Thesis, University of the Witwatersrand, Johannesburg, South Africa (2013).
10. Yue-Wu Li, Feng Qi, A new closed-form formula of the Gauss hypergeometric function at specific arguments, Axioms (2024) 13050317.